

Moving FAIR Vocabularies Forward For All: what are our priorities?

Notes from the day two group brainstorming session.

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Note that text from this document will be published online. Don't include identifying information

Key messages and sound-bites

- 'CV's - Controlled Vocab not real if not on-line
- 'Do not be seduced by partial solutions!'
- 'Local to Global'
- 'Machine Actionable'
- "Machine actionable metadata is more important than machine-readable"
- We need the 'I' in FAIR
- DOI's for vocabs
- Vocabs are often applied late in a project leading to later interoperability issues. The 'I' in FAIR means vocabs need to be considered at project outset.
- Vocabulary convergence
- API convergence / standardisation
- Mapping convergence (both tools and mappings)
 - Mapping to schema.org as an example
- Challenge - sheer volume of data, vocabs and mappings
- Registries - the proliferation can be due to people not knowing what is out there - index of registries? Identifier on a vocab?
- AI opportunities for the above
- Graph technology is becoming more prevalent - and has great power and promise
- Interest in ontologies and graph technology is growing
- © Master (Data) Chef - Mystery Box Challenge
- 'Data should be cooked with care'
- 'Responsible Service of Alcohol Data' (Ethics of VCs)
- Indigenous considerations and CARE principles
- 'Misappropriation of Data'
- 'Legitimacy' and 'Legitimate Use'

- Common theme: Excel (or other) -> SKOS -> OWL (Example from Francisca Oladipo - Africa - VODAN)

Some Resources (please add):

- Ten Simple Rules for making a vocabulary FAIR: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.02325>
- Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM): <https://academic.oup.com/database/article/doi/10.1093/database/baac035/6591806>
- <https://www.gida-global.org/care> Indigenous (CARE)
- [The WorldFAIR Project - The WorldFAIR Project \(worldfair-project.eu\)](http://www.worldfair-project.eu) - opportunities around FAIR Implementation Profiler (FIPs) (also Lesley W)
- See also Ontoportals O'FAIRe - graphical and numerical score of FAIRness
- Snap2Snomed <https://snap.snomedtools.org/>
- Indigenous research - a careful evolution - relevance of CARE guidelines <https://www.gida-global.org/care>
 - Collective Benefit
 - Authority to Control
 - Responsibility
 - Ethics

Brainstorming:

- Convergence is an overwhelming theme - in particular technical for interoperability
- Standardised data output across domains - SSSOM?
 - SKOS -> OWL -> SSSOM
 - Ontoserver -> SnapAGoGo -> SSSOM
 - NFA -> Resource Description & Access (RDA) -> SSSOM
 - ...
- API convergence for SKOS or other - from SSSOM or above?
- Adoption of FIPs across domains
- Ontoportals - cross-domain Ontology curation - do we need to learn more? SKOS import support, mappings etc. - Our community is invited to participate
- Health showed a need to undertake lots of mappings but this needs to be used to support convergence to nationally agreed standard / reference vocabularies for example SNOMED-CT.
- Health converging for now around national toolsets Ontoserver and Snap2Snomed.
- Health - rather than specifically looking at Vocab we are looking at vocab mapping mechanisms. Next steps are expanding the tool capability to cover use-cases such as automated and curated mappings and API functionality 'Machine Readable'. The aim would be to develop this with a domain agnostic intent. Extensive co-design will be required to ensure this meets the needs of stakeholders and non-technical groups involved in curation and vocab use.
- FHIR integration into Personal Online Datastores (PODs)
- Challenge - how do we choose the correct vocabulary & semantic interoperability
 - DOI's for vocabs (at RVA or external service like Zenodo?)

If you search and find, how do you select from more than one option?

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Summarisation

The conference was international demonstrating a real need for local, national and international convergence

- ARDC helping focus activities in Australia across domains
- Australian Vocabularies roadmap - will take on-board the findings and thoughts of today
- Conference was international which is fantastic and we have some clear areas to progress in the next year. The ARDC will need to decide on whether we run a conference next year.
- Would it be advantageous to align the RVA symposium with eResearch or similar?

Specific actions to take forward (please add here):

Roadmap incorporation of feedback from the symposium

Small specific next steps thoughts...

- Some terminologies can't be represented in RVA - perhaps we can understand that a bit more
- ARDC RVA work continuing in the health space - Research Terminologies Australia as a concept - where do we put those? Do we have the infrastructure to support
- Social science - possibly link co-design in that space at ARDC with SnapaGoGo co-design going into Q2 2024...
- How do we find out what is useful?
- Could RVA indicate which of its referenced vocabs are profiles vs unique as a way to indicate that another vocab has been used and then perhaps extended.

- CODATA 2023 WorldFAIR workshop on [Defining a Core Metadata Framework for Cross-Domain Data Sharing and Reuse](#)
- How-to - eg AGROVOC's
- adding provenance
- standards exist...
- reference the vocabulary in use
- Open call for external use of Ontoport API...
- International engagement - in light of the increasing popularity of knowledge graph application

About reuse of existing ontology terms and how to avoid reinventing the wheel.

There are some communities that prepared principles on how to reuse and build ontologies in the Biological and Biomedical domain, here is the [link](#) with the principles. I think this question came out during some of the talks from the Tuesday session.

Counterpoints to above paragraph: (1) the above link is a set of principles according to that group or its main developers. Some particular principles are valid, but as a whole it reflects an approach specific to them. It is not representative of the global community nor of the possible approaches or methods.

(2) the *not reinventing wheel analogy* has potential to do harm. insisting on not doing so is misleading in part because it assumes a valid analogy. I propose that the cliché should not be used any longer. It is misleading and does not necessarily apply to vocabularies, at least to ontologies or systems with specified meanings, formal semantics, and any assumptions thereto. Using that analogy is also at risk of being used more so as a tactic to gain users or for financial gain, as well as exclude alternative or competing systems. As another speaker correctly echoed on Nov 15, there is a political element. Distinct vocabularies on a perceived similar domain may be competitors, but may have different semantics and assumptions. In terms of string matching with no associated meaning, perhaps the analogy applies, but when semantics and any assumptions or abstract theory are associated with the terms or their referents, one cannot (and I argue should not) simply reuse without consequence, i.e. lest they wish to blindly accept those descriptions to label and describe their data or their expertise accordingly. Case in point: the above link goes to a group that implicitly assumes use of models (eg. upper or mid models) and a significant degree of semantic and ideological assumptions which largely go unknown, and unassessed or reviewed. It also very likely represents an example group with an implicit monopolization by specific models. Lastly, it would be wrong to say or imply the biomedical discipline as a whole is accurately and globally represented by that particular group or the contained models and vocabularies. There is a wider world out there with other actual or potential vocabs and models for the given discipline. For more on this see or contact <https://purl.org/rrovetto/ethics-of-ontology> (fyi: I've served in governance teams for it among other involvements and observations since 2009)